

Appendix C

Evaluation and testing questionnaires

Table C1

The questionnaire for the plausibility and usability testing of the framework (phases 1 and 2)

DSF Step №	DSF Step	Feedback form
1	Framework Guide	What is unclear and should be explained better? What should be added?
2	Context	What is unclear and needs additional comments? What context parameters should be added? What is the purpose of adding these context parameters? What context parameters should be removed? Why?
3	Goals	What is unclear and needs additional comments? What goals should be added? Why? What goals should be removed/renamed/combined? Why?
4	Challenges	What is unclear and needs additional comments? What challenges should be added? Why? What challenges should be removed/renamed/combined? Why?
5	Recommendations	Which recommendations are unclear? What should be added/explained better? (dropdown list) What additional recommendations can be given? (add recommendations in the format [Challenge]: [Recommendation (title, recommendation text, references)]) What recommendations are incorrect/inaccurate? Please provide a rationale. Design of the recommendations page (1) Is it necessary to reduce the page's text (e.g., move references to literature to an expandable block)? (2) Do we need to add graphic information (photographs, drawings, diagrams)? (3) Links to similar systems with features or designs that could make this framework better. Please add comments on what I should pay attention to in the specified system. General framework feedback

Table C2

The questionnaire for the impact testing of the framework (phase 3)

DSF Step №	DSF Step	Feedback form
2	Context	What is unclear and needs additional comments? How comprehensively can the set of contextual parameters describe your city regarding waste management? What context parameters or groups of context parameters should be added to make your city WM description more comprehensive and accurate? Please indicate the purpose of adding each additional context parameter or group of context parameters.
3	Goals	Are there any specific additional goals of WM system development and improvement in your city that were not indicated in the list of goals?
4	Challenges	Are there any specific additional challenges in your city that were not indicated in the list of challenges?
5	Recommendations	How would you rate the accuracy and applicability of the recommendations presented? What recommendations are incorrect/inaccurate? Please provide a rationale. Are there any recommendations that you will apply or are already using in your city? General framework feedback